

ISic2922

Epitaph for Laurentius, a doctor, and his wife Prosdocia

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

limestone

Object

tabula

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Syracusae

Place of origin (modern)

Siracusa

Provenance

Arancio hypogeum, villa Landolina

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Siracusa

Physical Description**Dimensions**

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout**Execution**

Engraved

Letter Forms**Letter heights:**

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. † Memoria Laurenti
2. medici et uxor eius
3. Prosdocia

Apparatus

Text of Korhonen 2010

Translation (en)

In memory of Laurentius the doctor and his wife Prosocia

Commentary**Digital identifiers:**

TM 175838

EDR 073823

EDCS 13900570

Bibliography

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 2012.0619

1888-. L'année épigraphique: revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine.. *L'année épigraphique : revue des publications épigraphiques relatives a l'antiquité romaine..* At 1951.0176

undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined, undefined 1876-.

Notizie degli scavi di antichità. *Notizie degli scavi di antichità.* At 189 no.3 fig.13

Agnello, S.L. 1950. Iscrizioni cristiane di Siracusa. *Rivista di Archeologia Cristiana.* 26: 221-222. At 222 no.6

Manganaro, G. 1993. Greco nei pagi e latino nelle città della Sicilia romana tra I e VI sec. d.C.. In Calbi, A., Donati, A., Poma, G.(eds.), *l'epigrafia del villaggio.* Faenza. pp. 543-594. At 584 no.2 fig.24

Lo Faro, Maria Domenica 2010. Osservazioni sugli ipogei di villa Landolina a Siracusa. *Archivio Storico Siracusano.* 45: 11-87. At 47-48 no.5

Korhonen, K. 2010. Greek and Latin in the urban and rural epigraphy of Byzantine Sicily. *Acta Byzantina Fennica.* n.s. 3: 116-135. At 121 no.2

Licensed under a Creative

Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic2922. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4356968>